

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERTISING FEATURES ON CONSUMERS' PURCHASE INTENTION

Mohamed Affan¹, Devaka Punchihewa², Piruni Deyalage³

Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura

¹affanmanzil@gmail.com, ²djp@sjp.ac.lk, ³piruni@sjp.ac.lk

Introduction

Nowadays social media plays a critical role in consumer buying decision process. A consumer undergoes a variety of steps prior to making a purchase choice. Consequently, the number of individuals who use social media as a platform for their business activities is increasing at an exponential rate. Particularly in Sri Lanka, social media exposure has grown exponentially, there are now more options for marketers to communicate with customers; as a result, customers base their purchasing decisions on the interactions they have with their peers on social media (Hasan & Sohail, 2020). Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube are three of the social media networks that are expanding at the quickest rates. Additionally, Instagram has become one of the most crucial social media sites for businesses to utilize (Saima & Khan, 2020).

Researcher has evaluated the relationship between social media and consumer purchasing behaviour (ZhuZ,2016). Gerald (2019) purportedly observed that 47% of total sales are influenced by social media advertising. Similarly, Roesler (2019) discovered that millennials made the bulk of online purchases. In addition, only a small number of studies have been

conducted in this field; accordingly, new research in the Sri Lankan context is required to fill this gap. Further analysis of prior research reveals that the majority of studies were conducted on the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention (Choedon and Lee, 2020). Other scholars have explored the nature of social media marketing (Isosuo, 2016). In addition, as demonstrated by a previous study, there is a dearth of research examining the effect of social media advertising features on customer purchase intention. In addition, there is no unanimity among previous studies regarding how to resolve this issue. Thus, a vacuum in the literature must be filled. Existing theories fall short of addressing this complex topic, and their support is insufficient to analyze the effect of social media advertising features on consumer purchase intention in Sri Lanka. Therefore, additional research is required to determine the effects of this phenomenon.

Research Questions

- What are the social media advertising features that affect consumer purchasing intention?
- What is the impact of identified social media advertising features on consumer purchasing intention?

Methodology

This investigation was conducted using quantitative research techniques. The research employed deductive approach. Data was collected via online questionnaires which included instruments with 5-point Likert scale to measure respondents' level of agreement on the constructs of the study. The

research design used was cross sectional study. The research has selected cluster sampling techniques as sampling techniques because it allows for creating clusters with a smaller representation of the population being assessed, with similar characteristics. Four provinces out of a total of nine were selected as sampling locations for the cluster sampling approach. The consumers were selected from provinces in Sri Lanka's Western, Central, North-western, and Southern regions for distribution to social media users. It was also required to have a minimum sample of 85 as per the Daniel Soper Sample Calculator. Multiple regression analysis was used as the data analysis technique.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework was developed after examining the research objectives (AliAbdallah Alalwan, 2018). Several research were inspected and this framework was used by most of the researchers.

Figure 2 Conceptual Framework

Results and Discussion

Demographic findings

110 responses were collected, and only 108 responses were used for further analysis. Out of the respondents, 52% were male and 48% were female. The majority of respondents were belonged to the age category of 26 and 35 and from the Northwestern province. The highest number of respondents were belonged to the annual income range of Rs. 50,000 and RS.100,000 and they mostly used Facebook, YouTube, and WhatsApp.

Descriptive Statistics

All of the mean values were between 4.08 and 4.33 and the standard deviation is 0.672. It indicated that, most of the people who answered were neutral, and that all of the values were in the upper range.

Normality Testing

Data is normally distributed if the skewness index is less than 3 and the kurtosis value is less than 10 (Kline ,2011). In the current study, Skewness and kurtosis are within the allowable range; therefore, data can be identified as being normally distributed.

Reliability and Validity Test

Internal consistency reliability was tested using Cronbach Alpha values. According to the analysis, Cronbach alpha values of all the construct were above 0.70 thereby satisfying the internal consistency reliability.

Convergent validity was tested using Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and all the constructs' AVE values were above 0.50 which satisfies the requirement of convergent validity. HTMT criterion was used by the author in order to test discriminant validity. It focuses with a mediated threshold of 0.85 and all the loadings should be below the line. And if none of the HTMT values are representing 1, it suggests that those HTMT values are significantly differs from 1 concluding that the discriminant validity has been met (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Based on the HTMT test results, the discriminant validity is ensured in this study.

Summary of hypothesis testing

Data analysis was done using multiple regression analysis. The adjusted R square value of the study was 0.564 which indicated that the independent variables explain 56.4% of the variation in consumer purchase intention. The summary of the hypotheses testing is presented in the table 1.

Table 1 : Hypotheses result

Hypotheses	Relationship	Justification	Status
H1	H1 – There is a positive effect of informativeness on consumer purchase intention	b = 0.144 p = 0.003	Accepted
H2	H2 – There is a positive effect of interactivity on consumer purchase intention	b = 0.473 p = 0.000	Accepted

H3	H3 – There is a positive effect of entertainment on consumer purchase intention	b = 0.312 p = 0.004	Accepted
H4	H4 – There is a positive effect of credibility on consumer purchase intention	b = 0.141 p = 0.002	Accepted

As per the above table, customer purchase intention can be positively affected by informativeness, interactivity, entertainment, and credibility. It was found that the features of social media advertising such as informativeness, interactivity, entertainment, and credibility have significant and favorable impact on the likelihood of a consumer making a purchase. All of the hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4 are supported in the study.

CONCLUSION

This study has investigated the social media advertising features and its effect on customer intention to purchase. Study results vary depending on the context of the study and the features used to describe social media advertising. It was discovered that social media advertising features such as informativeness, interactivity, entertainment, and credibility have a significant positive effect on consumer intent to purchase. Therefore, all the hypotheses were supported.

The theoretical implication of this research includes gaining a better knowledge of how different social media advertising features influence the purchase intention of the consumers of Sri Lanka. In this study, the

relationship between the efficacy of social media advertising and customer purchase intent was investigated using the theory of planned behavior. It was revealed that some of the most engaging elements of social media advertising had a positive effect on customers' purchasing intent. Therefore, this is a crucial contribution to comprehending the efficacy of social media advertising. In terms of managerial implications, the findings of this study will be useful to the corporate managers of Sri Lanka when designing social media advertising campaigns and decision making and Companies can be surer that their investment in social media advertising and related features will pay off in the form of higher sales and brand recognition.

In terms of limitations, this study considered only four features of social media advertising. However, there are lots subfactors that can influence customer purchasing intent which can be considered by the future researchers such as perceived relevance, Habit etc. Further the smaller sample size used for the study will make it difficult to generalize the findings of the study to the entire population. Therefore, future researchers can replicate the same study with a larger sample size.

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